

1 **A third cytokine, interferon gamma, functions in a minimal immunologic system with TNFa and**
2 **IL-1b.**

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7 We recently described a minimal immunologic system containing two vector components whose
8 expression was interrelated, TNF-alpha and interleukin-1b (IL-1b). We demonstrate here that a minimal
9 immunologic system contains a third component, interferon gamma. Interferon gamma was
10 distinguishable from alpha and beta interferons in quality of necessity in an immunologic system. The
11 ligand here likely serves to signal an undesirable entity, infection, danger, or a chronic foreign presence.

12 Citations

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